

Original Article

Detection of Aflatoxin B₁ and Ochratoxin-A in Sputum and Serum Samples from *Aspergillus* spp. of Asthma Patients Using Coconut Cream Agar and ELISA Technique

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Abstract

Objectives: The goal of this study was to determine whether the *Aspergillus* species isolated from asthmatic patients were mycotoxigenic or non mycotoxigenic fungi in the sputum and serum samples. **Methodology:** One hundred and twenty-eight samples of either gender and an age range of 3–78 years were collected from different places in Thi-Qar Province (Specialized Center for Respiratory Diseases, Al-Huda Center in Souq Al-Shuyoukh) from December 21st, 2021 to April 1st, 2022. They were divided into patients and healthy groups. Whereas the isolated *Aspergillus* genera were taken and cultured on the coconut agar medium and screening under UV light 360 nm, as well as the examination of each sample of sputum and serum by the ELISA technique. **Results:** All *Aspergillus* strains were positive with blue fluorescence on CCA media under UV light. This study found that the aflatoxins B₁ and ochratoxins-A was produced in sputum and serum samples in both the patient group and control group. Statistically, the patient groups showed a significant difference in levels by samples ($P \leq 0.05$) and the healthy groups showed a non-significant ($P > 0.05$). **Conclusions:** Most *Aspergillus* spp. Isolated from asthmatic patients were producers aflatoxin B₁ and ochratoxin-A on coconut agar medium and extract mycotoxins from (sputum about 68.42% and 40% of serum Samples) of aflatoxinsB₁ and from (sputum about 78.95% and 96.88% of serum Samples) of ochratoxin-A taken from asthmatic patients using ELISA technique.

Keywords: Asthma, Mycotoxin, Aflatoxin, Ochratoxin, *Aspergillus*, ELISA

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1. Introduction

Mycotoxins are toxic secondary metabolites produced naturally by certain filamentous fungi, mostly *Aspergillus*, *Alternaria*, *Fusarium*, and *Penicillium* under suitable environmental conditions [1]. They are mainly produced by some genera/species under suitable conditions such as temperature, water content, and pH [2]. These toxins affect

metabolic processes and cause disease and death in humans and animals [3]. Currently, more than 300 mycotoxins are known and possess wide variations in fungal origin, structure, function, and biological effect, but only a few of them appear to have a significant effect on health [4,5]. For example, Aflatoxins (Afs), Ochratoxins (OTA), Fumonisin (FBs), Deoxynivalenol (DON), Patulin, Zearalenone, type A Trichothecenes-T-2 and HT-2, type B Trichothecenes [6].

Aflatoxins are secondary metabolites of the molds *A. flavus* and *A. parasiticus*, and are of great concern because of their detrimental effects on the health of humans and animals, including carcinogenic, mutagenic, teratogenic, and immunosuppressive effects [7]. Abiotic factors such as temperature, water activity, pH, carbon, and nitrogen have a great influence on the aflatoxin biosynthesis pathway [8], but in particular, aflatoxin contamination is highly dependent upon temperature and water activity. Based on chromatographic and fluorescence characteristics, all aflatoxins known to date can be classified into 18 different types. There are many types of AFs, including AFB₁, AFB₂, AFG₁, AFG₂, AFM₁ and AFM₂. The main type is AFB₁ because it is classified as class 1 carcinogenic by the International Agency for Cancer Research (IACR). [9]. Aflatoxin B₁ is most commonly related to aflatoxicosis, as well as acute toxicity, chronic toxicity, carcinogenicity, teratogenicity, genotoxicity, and immunotoxicity [10].

Ochratoxins are mycotoxins produced by storage fungi, such as many species of *Penicillium* and *Aspergillus*, with ochratoxin A (OTA) being the most common. OTA production requires some factors like temperature, activity water (a_w), and low-consuming elements [11]. The formation of ochratoxin A (OTA) is dependent on fungous resources, product type, and geographical location [12]. OTA shows carcinogenic, nephrotoxic, teratogenic, immunotoxic, and neurotoxic properties. It has also been associated with nephropathy in humans [13].

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2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Study Design

This case-control study was conducted at the College of Science/University of Thi-Qar from November 15th, 2021 to November 15th, 2022. A total of 128 patients of both genders were within the age range of 3 to 78 years. The patients were divided into 2 groups. In group A, 98 patients with asthma, whereas in group B, 30 subjects with healthy control.

2.2. Coconut-based medium test

The Coconut Cream Agar (CCA) was prepared according to the manufacturer's instructions by suspending 50g of coconut cream and 2g of agar in 100ml of sterile D.W. Heat the media in the beaker on the heating centrifuge until it boils to dissolve the medium completely. Sterilize for 15 minutes in an autoclave at 15 pounds of pressure and 121 degrees Celsius. Allow 45-50°C to cool. Pour into sterile Petri dishes. After that, we prepared the sample suspension by taking 1ml of sterile normal saline and putting it in the eppendorf tube, and taking part of the colony using a sterile loop and mixing it with the normal saline using a vortex. The plate center was inoculated with 5 µl of spore suspension and incubated in the dark at 25°C. The presence or absence of a fluorescence ring in the agar surrounding the colonies under UV light after 3–7 days of incubation was noted, and the results were scored as positive or negative.

2.3. ELISA Technique

2.3.1. Detection of mycotoxins (Human Aflatoxin B₁; Human ochratoxin-A)

This kit is an Enzyme-Linked Immunosorbent Assay (ELISA). The plate has been pre-coated with the human (OCH-A; AKR7L) antibody. (OCH-A; AKR7L) present in the sample is added and binds to antibodies coated on the wells. And then biotinylated human (OCH-A; AKR7L) antibody is added and binds to (OCH-A; AKR7L) in the sample. Then Streptavidin-HRP is added and binds to the biotinylated (OCH-A; AKR7L) antibody. After incubation, unbound streptavidin-HRP is washed away during a washing step. Substrate solution is then added and color develops in proportion to the amount of Human (OCH-A; AKR7L). The reaction is terminated by the addition of an acidic stop solution, and absorbance is measured at 450 nm.

2.4. Statistical Analyses

The data of mycotoxins productions were examined using the SPSS Version 25 Test (Chi-square Test). The results of the statistical analysis were reported as X² value, the statistical significance level used was $P \leq 0.05$ for all factors.

3. Results

3.1. Screening for mycotoxin production by *Aspergillus* on Coconut Cream Agar

In the study, five strains of *Aspergillus* (*A. flavus*, *A. niger*, *A. terreus*, *A. clavaatus*, and *A. ochraceus*) isolated from sputum samples were tested for their capacity to produce mycotoxins. This method was conducted by using the fluorescence technique on CCA medium (Figure 1). All *Aspergillus* strains were positive with blue fluorescence on CCA media under UV light (Table 1).

Table 1. Qualitative screening of the ability of different fungal strains to produce mycotoxins on a coconut cream agar medium (CCA).

Strain	Mycotoxins production
<i>A. flavus</i>	+++
<i>A. niger</i>	+++
<i>A. clavaatus</i>	+
<i>A. ochraceus</i>	+
<i>A. terreus</i>	+

Key of test: (+) Traces of production, (+++) Strong production

Figure 1: The reverse of CCA cultures of *Aspergillus* isolated from asthmatic patients. The positive strains fluoresce blue, and negative non-fluoresce under UV light (365 nm) after 10 days at 25°C.

Table (2) demonstrates the aflatoxin B₁ levels in asthmatic patients' sputum and serum. As can be seen from Table 2 and figure 2, the sputum appears to be the best specimen to test when looking for aflatoxins. In sputum, (68.42%) of the samples were positive in asthma patients and the healthy (84.62%), whereas serum did not appear to be a good reservoir for aflatoxin detection. Levels of detection of mycotoxins in sputum samples reported in parts per billion (ppb) or ng/mL were determined to be (0.1-1.777) and serum samples were determined to be (0.01-0.500) ng/ml. whereas the levels of detection of mycotoxins in patient groups were higher than in healthy groups. Statistically, the patient groups showed a significant difference in levels by samples ($P \leq 0.05$) and the healthy groups showed a non-significant ($P > 0.05$).

Table 2. Specimen types tested for Aflatoxin B₁ from patients exposed to molds; statistical analysis of groups by using the Chi-square Test.

Sample Type	Patients group			Healthy group		
	Positive Samples NO. (%)	Negative Samples NO. (%)	Total	Positive Samples NO. (%)	Negative Samples NO. (%)	Total
Sputum	26 (68.42%)	12 (31.58%)	38	11 (84.62%)	2(15.38%)	13
Serum	12 (40%)	18 (60%)	30	2 (40%)	3 (60%)	5
Total	38	30	68	13	5	18
X ²	5.493 ^a			3.583 ^a		
P Value	0.019			0.058		

$P < 0.05$ = Significant; $P > 0.05$ = Non significant

Figure 2: depicts the distribution of aflatoxin B₁ in sputum and serum samples from (a) asthma patients and (b) healthy people.

Table 3 demonstrates the Ochratoxin-A levels in asthmatic patients' sputum and serum. As can be seen from Table 3 and Figure 3, the sputum appears to be the best specimen to test when looking for ochratoxin-A. Sputum samples were positive for asthma patients (78.95%) and healthy (92.31%), whereas serum samples were positive for asthma patients (96.88%) and healthy (100%). Levels of detection of mycotoxins in sputum samples reported in parts per billion (ppb) or ng/mL were determined to be (1–51) ng/ml and serum samples were determined to be (1–15) ng/ml. whereas the levels of detection of mycotoxins in patient groups were higher than in healthy groups. Statistically, the patient groups showed a significant difference in levels by samples ($P \leq 0.05$) and the healthy groups showed a non-significant ($P > 0.05$).

Table 3. Specimen types tested for Ochratoxin –A from patients exposed to molds, statistical analysis of groups by using Chi-square Test.

Sample Type	Patients group			Healthy group		
	Positive Samples NO. (%)	Negative Samples NO. (%)	Total	Positive Samples NO. (%)	Negative Samples NO. (%)	Total
Sputum	30 (78.95%)	8 (21.05%)	38	12 (92.31%)	1 (7.69%)	13
Serum	31(96.88%)	1 (3.12%)	32	8 (100%)	0	8
Total	61	9	70	20	1	21
X ²	4.983 ^a			0.646 ^a		
P Value	0.026			0.421		

$P < 0.05$ = Significant; $P > 0.05$ = Non significant

Figure 3. Depicts of the distribution of ochratoxin-A in sputum and serum samples from (a) asthma patients and (b) healthy people.

4. Discussion

4.1. Detection of Mycotoxigenic and mycotoxigenic fungi on coconut agar medium

The constituents of coconut have an effect on fluorescent pigment production in coconut culture. That blue fluorescence is a method used to develop a qualitative method for detecting aflatoxigenic *Aspergillus* species grown in the specific medium [14].

The use of coconut media to detect the presence or absence of aflatoxin content is considered ineffective due to the high sensitivity of *Aspergillus* to the composition of coconut medium [15] reported coconut cream agar (50% coconut cream) to be more effective than a medium made with dried coconut. The current study found that *A. flavus* and *A. niger* (+++), *A. clavatus*, *A. ochraceus*, and *A. terreus* (+) produce

mycotoxins. These results disagree with Yazdani *et al.* [16] where negative results were recorded for all isolates of *Aspergillus* used in his study. The florescent ring did not appear under UV.

4.2. Detection of production of Aflatoxin B₁ (AFs) and Ochratoxin-A (OTA) using ELISA Technique

ELISA is a routine screening tool for the rapid monitoring of mycotoxins that offers high sensitivity, affordability, and ease of analysis [17]. Advantages of ELISA include, in addition to the specificity of antibody-antigen binding, a relatively low limit of detection (LOD), high sample throughput with low sample volume and minimal clean-up procedures, and ease of application [18,19]. However, this method is not so reliable in the case of complex matrices, is quite time-consuming and the kits are for single use and are not suitable for field-testing [20].

A wide range of commercial ELISA-based kits are available for different matrices, including human serum, which makes it a highly versatile methodology. However, the potential for cross-reactivity with metabolites of target compounds or matrix components can give rise to overestimated values [21]. For this reason, AOAC International has not approved any ELISA method [22], and positive results must be confirmed (e.g., through chromatographic methods).

There have been no previous studies that have demonstrated large numbers of different body fluids to be contaminated with mycotoxins. This study shows that mycotoxins can be found in body fluids (sputum and serum) in humans after environmental exposure to toxin-producing molds.

This study found that the positive samples of aflatoxins B₁ and ochratoxins-A were higher than the negative samples in both the patient group and control group in sputum samples. And it showed that the patient samples were more productive of mycotoxins than the control samples. As for the serum samples, it was found that the negative samples were higher than the positive samples of aflatoxin B₁ for patients and controls. As for ochratoxin-A, the positive samples were very high for patients and control. These results of the study contradict those of Hooper *et al.* [23], where it was found that negative samples were higher than positive samples for aflatoxin B₁ and ochratoxins-A in sputum samples

5. Conclusions

The findings of this study found that most *Aspergillus* spp. isolated from the respiratory tract of asthmatic patients were mycotoxigenic fungi due to produced mycotoxins on coconut cream agar medium (CCA) when screening under UV light. Aflatoxin B₁ and Ochratoxin-A were detected from sputum and serum samples, where these mycotoxins can be detected in sputum more than serum samples.

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Conflicts of Interest: The authors declare no conflict of interest

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